

ASSESSMENT OF COUNSELORS NEEDS AMIDST MODERN CHALLENGES

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ABSTRACT

Frequently, counselors are not given enough attention. In fact, only a few studies have been done focusing on their well-being and their needs that might affect their overall performance and ability to help the community. The purpose of this study is to unveil the level of common needs of twenty (20) school counselors of San Beda College Alabang (SBCA) along with certain variables, such as age, sex, department assignment, undergraduate degree, and years spent as counselors, which at one point may have affected their needs. This paper also aims to reveal what specific demographic criteria do the needs of SBCA school counselors call for attention and possible strengthening. Responses gathered were analyzed using the Kruskal-Wallis H test, Mann-Whitney U test, t-test, and frequency, and percentage. Findings show that generally, a mean score of 3.11 for Physical Needs states that it is “Somewhat of a Need” all for San Beda College Alabang counselors. Hence, the Kruskal Wallis H test draws out a p-value of 0.023 and 0.014 for Emotional Needs and Social Needs, respectively, when common needs were compared in terms of department assignment. Post hoc analysis using the Dunn-Bonferroni test revealed that Social Needs of counselors in the Higher Education Department are significantly higher than all other departments. In conclusion, in terms of the wellbeing of counselors, study reveals that those in the Higher Education Department has significantly higher emotional needs than those in the other Departments and counselors regardless of demographics, are in need of strengthening their physical wellbeing in San Beda College Alabang in the Philippines.

Keywords: assessment, councilor, physical wellbeing, challenges